

Sustainability Performance of Community Extension Services Programs of Saint Mary's University: Setting Future Directions

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ABSTRACT

The study was undertaken to assess the sustainability performance of SMU Extension Services Programs in terms of extent of importance and practice along the following domains: social, environmental, and economic. An action plan was crafted to address challenges of the extension programs and set directions for school flagship extension program. The mixed methods research was carried out with the use of survey questionnaires and by scanning relevant documents to generate the respondents' assessment of sustainability performance of the extension programs and to determine the sustainability challenges. The respondents of the study included stakeholders like Mission and Identity Coordinators, the LMCDAC director and staff, and community organizers of the different flagship programs of each school from SY 2015-2016 TO SY 2018-2019. Findings revealed that there are social, economic, and environmental activities that are considered of moderate to great importance, and also either of moderate or great practice making such extension activities generally sustainable. The findings further revealed the positive values and attitudes that SMU stakeholders, particularly the implementers, hold towards the extension programs. Seeing that there are of great important extension activities but of little extent of practice signifies the SMU stakeholders' willingness to do more noble activities in the communities. Activities that are of great importance but little extent of practice should be reviewed for consideration for future extension planning, if necessary and within the capability of the University.

Keywords: *community engagement, university extension, community involvement*

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability can be measured using its three pillars namely: environmental, social and economic (Kahn, 1995). There is a need to be guided by these factors to make any program exist for what it has been intended to be. The sustainability performance of the SMU Extension Program was therefore looked into to develop an action plan and set future directions for the various schools' flagship extension programs.

The Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order No. 53 (CMO No. 52, s. 2016) indicates that the dynamic synergy of research, extension and instruction is the indispensable, foundational, distinctive, and specialized hallmark of universities. It further points out that Extension programs in higher education institutions provide the space to discover practical, evidence, and science-based answers that can address real-world social, economic, and environmental challenges of partner communities. This implies that a university can make its academic and research endeavors more relevant when carried out in collaboration with communities such as industry, local businesses, or community groups. Also, Republic Act 7722, otherwise known as the Higher Education Act of 1994 creating the Commission on Higher Education mandates institutions of higher learning to respond to the call for societal transformation. The aim is to serve the poorest of the poor, the less privileged, the deprived and the oppressed (Elman, 1998).

Meanwhile, the mission of Saint Mary's University as a Filipino, Catholic and Missionary institution includes among others the pursuit of quality and excellent education for local and global relevance and responsiveness, and the development of community-supportive persons promoting multi-ethnicity, social justice, peace and integrity of God's creation. This missionary mission is generally manifested in the extension programs the different university units carry out, where each unit has its own flagship program.

The extension programs are under the Lingkod Maria Community Development and Advocacy Center (LMCDAC) which has crafted the goals and orientations to address the Christian Mission of the SMU. The LMCDAC serves as the clearing house of all outreach and community extension services of the six major schools and their flagship programs in the university namely: School of Accountancy and Business (*PABookaS and Entrep sa Barangay*); School of Engineering, Architecture and Information Technology (*Tulungan sa Teknolohiya*); School of Health and Natural Sciences (*Jesus Mobile Clinic*); School of Teacher Education and the Humanities (*Nanumo nga Pagadalan*); School of Graduate Studies (*The GIFTED Program*); and the College of Law (*Peace, Justice and Human Rights Program*). The apostolate for the

indigenous peoples is interwoven in these outreach and extension flagship programs of the university (SMU Lingkod Maria 2019 MOPG).

The presence, implementation, outcomes and effectiveness of SMU extension program was evaluated by Valtoribio, Villanueva, Jubay and Taroma in 2018. Results showed that in terms of presence of systems, SMU through CESC, has a clear-cut policy on extension activities. Each school anchors its set of guidelines on CESC. In terms of implementation, every school follows procedures from planning to implementation. The schools had signed MOAs with their respective partners for some specific activities. In terms of outcomes and effectiveness, the extension activities of the different schools were rated from good to very good.

However, a number of gray areas were also pointed out: activities of the schools are not simply focused on the flagship programs – other activities branched out from immediate concerns particularly when there are calamities; community clients were requesting for more trainings which oftentimes not addressed due to time element; and financial support to start-up their own businesses after the trainings. The program implementers generally could not cope with the demands of the communities, and so the question on sustainability of the programs arises: Could we sustain the flagship programs that link SMU to the communities, which makes the curricular programs more relevant and purposeful?

Sustainable development means ensuring the co-evolution of the economic, social and environmental systems, with appropriate and well-balanced policies that are backed by good governance (Klarin, 2018). It should be able to respond to future challenges, such as achieving balance between socio-economic development and the environment, reducing pollution and environmental degradation, exploiting natural resources, reducing harmful gas emissions and climate impacts, reducing poverty and hunger, achieving world peace and other serious challenges and threats faced by humanity (WCED, 1987). It is also a process of changes, where resources are raised, the direction of investments is determined, the development of technology is focused and the work of different institutions is harmonized, thus the potential for achieving human needs and desires is increased as well (Vare and Scott, 2007).

This study assessed the sustainability performance of the SMU Community Extension Services Programs in terms of extent of importance and practice along social, environmental, and economic domains and set future directions for school flagship extension programs. Action plan was crafted to address challenges of the extension programs and set directions for school flagship extension program.

The goals, orientations, as well as prospective activities of LMCDAC have been classified into the Three Dimensional View of Sustainability by Bruntland Commission (WCED, 1987) and the Triple Bottom Line Model by John Elkington (Lima, 2017) in defining Sustainability. The Social, Environment, and Economic dimensions of sustainability by Bruntland Commission are referred to as People, Planet, and Profit, respectively, in the Triple Bottom Line Model by John Elkington. The terms of Bruntland and Elkington may appear different but they mean the same ideas. However, this study used the three pillars of sustainability offered by Bruntland Commission, namely, social, environmental, and economic, which is considered more appropriate in evaluating the sustainability performance of SMU'S Extension Programs.

Results of the study can be used by the administration, curriculum implementers, school deans, heads and supervisors to re-think and redesign the extension programs to make the curricular programs more globally and locally responsive and relevant. It can also help the community organizers to realize the nobility of the programs and thereby motivate and inspire them to collaborate and engage themselves actively in the different extension programs being promoted by the University for the common and greater good of concerned stakeholders.

METHODOLOGY

A mixed methods research design was used in the study. Both quantitative and qualitative techniques were utilized. The quantitative technique was used to generate the stakeholders' assessment of sustainability performance of the extension programs in terms of extent of importance and practice along social, environmental, and economic factors of sustainability. On the other hand, the qualitative technique of document scanning and interviews were used to determine sustainability challenges and also to validate the responses derived from the survey conducted. The respondents of the study included stakeholders like Mission and Identity Coordinators, the LMCDAC director and staff, and community organizers of the different flagship programs of each school from SY 2015-2016 TO SY 2018-2019. *Sustainability performance assessment* is a paradigm for thinking about the future in which environmental, societal, and economic considerations are balanced in the pursuit of an improved quality of life (UNESCO). In this study, it refers to determining the extent of importance and practice of the social, environmental, and economic dimensions of the extension programs at

Saint Mary's University. Moreover, extension programs along a particular dimension (social, economic, or environmental) may be considered *sustainable* if they are considered at least of moderate importance and moderate practice. An assessment of low importance and low practice may be considered *not sustainable*. *Social sustainability* refers to identifying and managing business impacts, both positive and negative, on people specifically on decent livelihood, fair trading practices, labor rights, equity, human safety, and health, and cultural diversity. *Environmental sustainability* refers to the maintenance of the factors and practices that contribute to the quality of environment on a long-term basis specifically atmosphere, water, land, biodiversity, materials and energy, and animal welfare. *Economic sustainability* consists of identifying the factors affecting investment, vulnerability, product quality and information, and the local economy. To gather the information needed in the study, floating of questionnaires, interviews and document scanning were carried out. Specifically, the following steps were undertaken: First, float and retrieve the survey questionnaires among the respondents; second, analyze the responses of the respondents on the perceived importance and actual practice vis-à-vis the three indicators (environmental, social, and economic aspects) and lastly, craft an action plan based on the items considered significant but not being practiced. The individual and overall means of items for practice and importance were computed to determine the sustainability performance.

The study was conducted with the researchers observing strict confidentiality and with the respondents' permission and informed consent. Ethical considerations like nonmaleficence, beneficence, scientific validity, and justice were applied to the study process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SECTION 1. Sustainability Performance of SMU Extension Services Programs in terms of Extent of Importance and Practice

A. SOCIAL

Out of 39 items, 37 were rated greatly important, while two items were rated moderately important. These two items include jail visitation (mean = 3.467) and facilitating community seed banks to establish and develop a collection of genetic plant resources for recovering traditional crops and sharing these resources with other communities (mean = 3.467). Jail visitation may sound noble, but being not familiar with the persons deprived of liberty might create a privacy problem. Meanwhile, facilitating community seed banks may be beyond the reach of SMU faculty and students because the activity requires a substantial funding and expertise on seeds and plant resources.

Nonetheless, top on the list of greatly important social extension activities but practiced to a moderate extent include the following:

- 1) Enhance the knowledge and competencies of children and youth and other disadvantaged groups through multi-disciplinary capacities or liberal education.**

The School of Teacher Education and Humanities (STEH) as well as the School of Graduate Studies have been conducting activities along this line. For instance, aside from collaborative activities on professional and personal enhancement of the teachers of the Diocese of Bayombong, STEH had also ventured into educating young children of the community with their *Nanumo nga Pagadalan*, and AKLAT. STEH also engaged in enhancing the leadership potentials the youth by conducting leadership exploration and development activities for the high school students of the Diocese of Bayombong.

The same holds for the Graduate Studies that has its Graduate Initiatives for Training, Empowerment, and Development (GIFTED). The program is focused on providing trainings, workshops and consultancy to groups of individuals or communities who need development assistance, particularly in the fields of arts and sciences, education, business, accounting, engineering, information technology, public administration and governance, and health care. Extension activities in the Graduate Studies are incorporated in relevant subject areas. Seminars have been conducted not only for public and private school teachers but even for out-of-school youth and students of DepED's alternative learning system. Nonetheless, the respondents might still find the activities insufficient to truly empower stakeholders; thus, the rating of moderate extent.

The finding is supported by the study of Valtoribio, Jubay, Villanueva, and Taroma (2019) which revealed that the pace of the training sessions and the convenience of the training schedules were rated the lowest along the area of content and structure. This may be due to the fact that the trainings were conducted during the teachers' summer break when they were supposed to be having relaxed moments with their families. Moreover, written comments in the evaluation mentioned about having too many topics in so short

a time. Many teacher trainees would like longer time for the various topics, particularly those they found difficult to teach. This observation conforms to the result on extent of knowledge and skills gained which were given relatively good ratings, indicating that the teacher trainees did not really absorb everything that they wanted to learn from the sessions.

2) Promote environmental justice through a defined advocacy with respect to sustaining the integrity of God's creation

The STEH Community Extension Service through the *Nanumo nga Pagadalan* engages its members in various CICM advocacies and social issues and concerns. One of the aims of the project is promote environmental justice through a defined advocacy with respect to sustaining the integrity of God's creation. Ecological Integrity is integrated in the *Nanumo nga Pagadalan* which seeks to form teachers, students, and beneficiaries who are respectful of the environment as a Common Home. This area was rated as of great importance but moderately practiced.

In an interview with Dr. Darwin Dacles, the former Director of LMCDAC and Director of Indigenous Knowledge and Traditions, he mentioned that they conducted a study on how Iwaks cope in a changing world together with Dr. Fe Yolanda del Rosario and Mr. Leonard Clemens Cadoy. The study documented their practices/steps involved in the Iwaks' system of cultivation, underlying changes that have taken place in the practice across time and, the importance of technology in their overall survival.

3) Raise awareness among IP communities on the potential values of indigenous knowledge, systems and practices for their growth and development

This is actually one of the aims for community extension services of the Indigenous Knowledge and Tradition Center (IKATC). This must have stemmed from its mission of preserving, promoting, and protecting indigenous knowledge, systems and practices including arts, traditions, ceremonies, and languages for the growth and development of the Peoples of Indigenous Cultural Communities (IKAT MOPG, 2017). All stakeholders of the University are generally enjoined to conduct activities geared towards this fold. The respondents of this study might have realized that greater awareness could have been developed among the faculty and students but not much with specific IP communities; thus, the perceived moderate extent of practice.

4) One-time and immediate need assistance to victims of disasters and calamities, or occasional gift-giving such as Alay Kapwa or Alay Pamasko, including feeding program

There are outreach activities being conducted regularly by the different schools and organizations in the University; however, the response to calls for assistance in times of emergencies is not really immediate. In most cases, the University, through some designated offices, solicit the generosity of faculty, employees, and students to be able to reach out to those who are in dire need of help.

The respondents might be wishing that the University has always stocks of goods that can be readily accessed when times get really hard for victims of disasters and calamities.

5) Indigenous peoples' advocacy activities

The CICM through SMU works with stakeholders, particularly the poor, the marginalized, and those at the remotest areas, and this includes but not limited to, the Peoples of Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs). Thus, the IKAT section envisions itself to be a premier advocate of indigenous peoples' concerns in Northern Luzon or the *Amianan* dedicated to empowering the peoples of Indigenous Cultural Communities (ICCs) for self-determination, growth and development. Its mission is to preserve, promote, and protect indigenous knowledge, systems and practices including arts, traditions, ceremonies, and languages for the growth and development of the Peoples of Indigenous Cultural Communities (i.e. *Hukhukyung Integrated Community Development Program spearheaded by the LMCDAC*).

6) Sharing of knowledge and lesson through exchange visits

This activity was identified as important to a great extent and practiced to a low extent. However, based on the MOPG and Program Portfolios of the different programs, it was not listed as one of the activities.

7) Deliver services in education appropriate to the needs of poor children including the youth and adults/parents, the indigenous peoples and other target groups and increase their access to those services.

STEH, IKATC, and CESC are in charge of such activities. Moreover, the University provides scholarships to deserving IPs and other underprivileged groups, thus enabling them to have access to education. In SY 2017-2018, there were 61 IP students who were given BIBAK discounts amounting to P 62,946. BIBAK discounts is given to students from Bontoc, Ifugao, Benguet, Apayao, and Kalinga (BIBAK). There were no discounts given in SY 2019-2020. Although, aside from BIBAK discounts, some IP students also avail of other discounts, like Working Scholars' Discounts, Library Working Scholars' Discounts, Academic Discounts, Service Grants (SCC, The Marian and ROTC), and those with siblings in the university enjoy the brother/sister discount.

The Center for Natural Sciences (CNS) also provides services to schools in Nueva Vizcaya for science laboratory procedures. The perceived moderate practice might be due to the fact that activities are not continuously done, and monitoring is not sustained.

8) Integrate Christian values formation to functional literacy promotion as characterized by Marian education

This activity is taken care of by STEH, particularly its BEED program students with their *Nanumo a Pagadalan*. The students teach 3Rs to children from nearby communities; but just like the others, the activities are not sustained because student implementers come to teach only when they have spare time from their hectic schedules.

9) Document cultural resources within Indigenous Peoples communities for an effective piece of community action

In an interview with Dr. Darwin Dacles, the former Director of LMCDAC and Director of Indigenous Knowledge and Traditions, he mentioned that they conducted a study on how I'waks cope in a changing world together with Dr. Fe Yolanda del Rosario and Mr. Leonard Clemens Cadoy. The study documented the ethno-ecological adaptation of the I'waks and see how these adaptive strategies have changed or been sustained over time. The study also documented their practices/steps involved in the I'waks' system of cultivation, underlying changes that have taken place in the practice across time and, the importance of technology in their overall survival.

Meanwhile, the following are also found on top of the list of greatly important activities but practiced to a low extent:

1. Subsidize food, healthcare, and education
2. Enhance IP capacities to lead IP awareness, advocacy, education and training and other issues that concern them
3. Ensure that underserved and marginalized sectors are afforded continuing education on justice, peace, and human rights.
4. Forge external linkages and intra-unit partnerships for the preservation, protection, promotion and empowerment of the Indigenous Peoples.
5. IP education

Table 1. Assessed Importance and Extent of Practice of Social Activities

Mean	Qd		A. SOCIAL	Mean	Qd
3.767	Great extent	1	Raise awareness among IP communities on the potential values of indigenous knowledge, systems and practices for their growth and development.	2.717	Moderate extent
3.767	Great extent	2	Enhance IP capacities to lead in IP awareness, advocacy, education and training and other issues that concern them.	2.450	Low extent
3.717	Great extent	3	Forge external linkages and intra-unit partnerships for the preservation, protection, promotion and empowerment of the Indigenous Peoples.	2.417	Low extent

Mean	Qd		A. SOCIAL	Mean	Qd
3.733	Great extent	4	Document cultural resources within Indigenous Peoples communities for an effective piece of community action.	2.517	Moderate extent
3.683	Great extent	5	Empower target communities or groups by increasing their human, social and leadership assets.	2.450	Low extent
		6	Work on Development Projects in collaboration with the Center's internal units and external partners.		
3.717	Great extent		a. IP education	2.483	Low extent
3.633	Great extent		b. IP Youth, Elderly, and Women's Activities	2.400	Low extent
3.517	Great extent		c. Legal Assistance	1.950	Low extent
3.517	Great extent		d. Health Assistance and Health Education	2.050	Low extent
3.567	Great extent	7	Conduct of activities in the school for enhancing multicultural awareness and concern for IP self-identity.	2.533	Moderate extent
3.583	Great extent	8	Conduct of cultural programs or presentations for sustained education and promotion of multi-ethnicity in the University and IP self-identity.	2.783	Moderate extent
3.567	Great extent	9	Promotion of creative expressions highlighting IP material and non-material cultural elements such as songs, dances, and oral traditions (legends, myths, stories, rituals, etc.).	2.550	Moderate extent
3.617	Great extent	10	Evangelize and humanize works and efforts for the IPs.	2.467	Low extent
3.683	Great extent	11	Indigenization of the liturgy (during special occasions) considering the multi-ethnic character of the University.	2.700	Moderate extent
3.533	Great extent	12	Incorporation of IP blend in the regular liturgy via songs, dances and worship.	2.533	Moderate extent
3.733	Great extent	13	deliver services in education appropriate to the needs of poor children including the youth and adults/parents, the indigenous peoples and other target groups and increase their access to those services.	2.717	Moderate extent
3.733	Great extent	14	Integrate Christian values formation to functional literacy promotion as characterized by Marian education.	2.883	Moderate extent
3.650	Great extent	15	Develop livelihood strategies and help alleviate hunger and poverty and other challenges that various communities may encounter.	2.433	Low extent
3.583	Great extent	16	Improve the health of the target clientele and promote the capacity of these groups to deal with health problems.	2.317	Low extent
3.750	Great extent	17	Ensure that underserved and marginalized sectors are afforded continuing education on justice, peace and human rights.	2.250	Low extent
3.767	Great extent	18	One-time and immediate need assistance to victims of disasters and calamities, or occasional gift-giving such as Alay Kapwa or Alay Pamasko, including feeding program.	3.367	Moderate extent
3.633	Great extent	19	Mobilize the Marian community to respond to emergencies.	3.083	Moderate extent
		20	Mobilization of some civic action duties and activities that conform to various community extension services such as:		
3.583	Great extent		a. blood-letting	2.467	Low extent
3.550	Great extent		b. information drive on health-related matters	2.483	Low extent
3.550	Great extent		c. drug abuse prevention	2.367	Low extent
3.700	Great		d. voter's education and other citizenship	2.417	Low

Mean	Qd		A. SOCIAL	Mean	Qd
	extent		education		extent
3.467	Moderate extent		e. jail visitation	2.533	Moderate extent
3.600	Great extent		f. liturgical and sacramental services	2.883	Moderate extent
3.700	Great extent		g. feeding program	2.717	Moderate extent
3.717	Great extent		h. Alay Kapwa donations	3.433	Moderate extent
3.767	Great extent		i. indigenous peoples' advocacy activities	3.167	Moderate extent
3.717	Great extent	21	Strengthen Christian generosity and volunteerism in responding to the present emerging issues and concerns of the indigenous peoples and other identified groups toward poverty alleviation, hunger, health, good governance, literacy and gender and development.	3.017	Moderate extent
3.767	Great extent	22	Promote environmental justice through a defined advocacy with respect to sustaining the integrity of God's creation.	2.933	Moderate extent
3.883	Great extent	23	Enhance the knowledge and competencies of children and youth and other disadvantaged groups through multi-disciplinary capacities or liberal education.	2.983	Moderate extent
3.633	Great extent	24	Impart the knowledge and expertise of engineering, architecture and information technology professionals to target clients and beneficiaries for their literacy and empowerment.	2.417	Low extent
3.700	Great extent	25	Conduct of medical services which was made possible through a collaborative planning with the stakeholders.	2.483	Low extent
3.600	Great extent	26	Provide health and medical services to the identified poor and underserved communities in the province.	2.533	Moderate extent
3.667	Great extent	27	Protection of religious beliefs and practices of indigenous peoples.	2.817	Moderate extent
3.567	Great extent	28	Assist in the preservation of music, traditional Instruments, dance, stories, songs, poetry, proverbs, riddles, etc. of indigenous peoples.	2.400	Low extent
3.650	Great extent	29	Crafting of project proposals on the establishment of the Marian Convergence Center (Dap-ayan).	2.100	Low extent
3.633	Great extent	30	Crafting of project proposals on the establishment of Library Cultural Study Section (in tandem with the ULRC).	2.350	Low extent
3.550	Great extent	31	Crafting of project proposals on Social Entrepreneurship Program (VPMI).	2.033	Low extent
3.567	Great extent	32	Promoting the integration of all stakeholders in decision-making on the landscape, especially women and youth.	2.150	Low extent
3.550	Great extent	33	Implement alternative community-based subsistence activities to relieve pressure on conservation areas.	2.167	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	34	Facilitate community seed banks to establish and develop a collection of genetic plant resources for recovering traditional crops and sharing these resources with other communities.	1.850	Low extent
3.567	Great extent	35	Document local knowledge of traditional and sustainable practices of natural resource use.	2.450	Low extent
3.567	Great extent	36	Mobilizing and engaging marginalized and vulnerable groups in project preparation, implementation and monitoring, and creating enabling environments for their social inclusion at the local level.	2.373	Low extent
3.650	Great extent	37	Address 'wellness needs' of the population.	2.483	Low extent
3.783	Great extent	38	Subsidize food, health care, and education.	2.367	Low extent

Mean	Qd		A. SOCIAL	Mean	Qd
3.750	Great extent	39	Sharing of knowledge and lessons through exchange visits.	2.550	Moderate extent
3.647	Great extent		Overall mean	2.539	Moderate extent

Meanwhile, the respondents assessed extent of practice differently from extent of importance. While importance was rated either moderate or great, practice was rated from low to moderate. Twenty-two of the 50 activities were rated practiced to a moderate extent, while more than half (56%) were rated practiced to a low extent. The top activities considered having great importance were practiced either to a moderate extent or low extent. Among those in the top list considered of great importance but practiced to a low extent are the following: enhance the knowledge and competencies of children and youth and other disadvantaged groups through multi-disciplinary capacities or liberal education, promote environmental justice through a defined advocacy with respect to sustaining the integrity of God's creation, raise awareness among IP communities on the potential values of indigenous knowledge, systems and practices for their growth and development, one-time and immediate need assistance to victims of disasters and calamities, or occasional gift-giving such as Alay Kapwa or Alay Pamasko, including feeding program, indigenous peoples' advocacy activities, sharing of knowledge and lesson through exchange visits, deliver services in education appropriate to the needs of poor children including the youth and adults/parents, the indigenous peoples and other target groups and increase their access to those services, integrate Christian values formation to functional literacy promotion as characterized by Marian education, and document cultural resources within Indigenous Peoples communities for an effective piece of community action.

While SMU faculty and students participate in one-time and immediate need assistance to victims of disasters and calamities as the need arises, and occasional gift-giving such as Alay Kapwa or Alay Pamasko every December, information dissemination to the faculty participants could be one of the problems and not everyone could join because the slots and rides are limited. The School of Teacher Education (STEH) leads in enhancing the knowledge and competencies of children and youth and other disadvantaged groups through multi-disciplinary capacities or liberal education together with the School of Graduate Studies. STEH through their Nanumo a Pagadalan conducts Christian values formation to functional literacy promotion as characterized by Marian Education. Hectic schedules from both faculty and student implementers were seen as problems and there were too many topics being discussed in a short time. Other activities focused on Indigenous Peoples communities through raising awareness on the potential knowledge, systems, and practices for their growth and development, IP advocacy activities and delivering services in education. Activities are not continuously done and monitoring is not sustained were identified as problems.

According to Kahn (1995), social sustainability encompasses notions of equity, empowerment, accessibility, participation, sharing, cultural identity, and institutional stability. It seeks to preserve the environment through economic growth and the alleviation of poverty. Some commentators have suggested that poor countries must accept environmental degradation as a short-term consequence of economic development. Others have argued that an enabling environment that optimizes resource allocation can obviate the need for such a trade-off.

Also, Slaper & Hall (2011) has identified variables that contribute to the social sustainability of community or region and could include measurements of education, equity and access to social resources, health and well-being, quality of life, and social capital.

B. ENVIRONMENTAL

Table 2 shows the respondents' assessment of the importance of environmental activities vis-à-vis the extent of practice of the said activities. Extent of importance among the items ranges from moderate to great extent, although the overall mean generally suggests great importance of environmental activities. Specifically, twenty-one of the 29 environmental activities are considered of great importance, while eight are considered of moderate importance. Among the twenty-one activities considered of great importance, setting up programs to recycle recyclables, and promoting management and recycling of solid wastes, obtained the highest mean (3.717), which signifies the respondents' utmost concern for solid waste management. This must be true because solid wastes abound everywhere even in schools and households.

The prevailing climate change might have also made the respondents realize the value of encouraging the commitment of the clientele to develop skills in formulating solutions to environmental problems and community plans for environmental protection placed, thus making this as the second highest (3.700) of great importance.

Two activities obtained the third highest mean of 3.683. The first is conducting environmental education, advocacy campaigns and a provision for action-based projects geared toward environmental protection and management. This must be a consequence for the need to formulate solutions to environmental problems. The people have to be educated first and be made to realize the long-term negative effects of environmental problems. The second which can be a result of being able to understand the whole situation is community education on the benefits of maintaining and conserving forests. Nueva Vizcaya is hailed as “watershed haven and agro-forestry” (Regional Development Council, Cagayan Valley), thus the extreme need to maintain and conserve forests.

Other activities that were relatively given the highest means include conducting tree planting campaigns and restoring forests throughout the basin (3.650); inculcating awareness and understanding of the interdependence between human beings and nature (3.650); providing strategic actions to help disaster-prone communities in reducing the risk of natural hazards and how they will manage disasters/calamities that may occur (3.633); promoting the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in land and water ecosystems in Nueva Vizcaya (3.617); and lastly, promoting environmental education programs or organic production and soil conservation (3.617). Apparently, the respondents accorded the aforementioned activities the highest priority in terms of importance.

The item promoting fuel-efficient heating and cooking stoves was rated moderately important, and it also received the lowest mean (3.373). This might be because people in Nueva Vizcaya have access to both modern and traditional modes of cooking. Cooking with charcoal or dry woods is still highly practiced in the province; so, people who cannot afford the modern way have a choice that is less costly.

Table 2. Assessed Importance and Extent of Practice of Environmental Activities

Importance			A. ENVIRONMENTAL	Practice	
Mean	QD			Mean	QD
3.650	Great extent	1	Inculcate awareness and understanding of the interdependence between human beings and nature.	2.900	Moderate extent
3.700	Great extent	2	Encourage the commitment of the clientele to develop skills in formulating solutions to environmental problems and community plans for environmental protection.	2.750	Moderate extent
3.683	Great extent	3	Conduct of environmental education, advocacy campaigns and a provision for action-based projects geared toward environmental protection and management.	2.883	Moderate extent
3.583	Great extent	4	Establishment of Community Forests by planting woody plants and fruit trees.	2.667	Moderate extent
3.550	Great extent	5	Protection and sustainable management of water sources, including restoration of rivers.	1.983	Low extent
3.500	Great extent	6	Improvement of drainage systems and water management practices.	1.833	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	7	Restore and protect watersheds and their associated ecosystem services;	1.917	Low extent
3.500	Great extent	8	Managing water and water systems more effectively, and enhancing soil water retention and water conservation through appropriate infrastructure, such as water harvesting structures.	1.800	Low extent
3.650	Great extent	9	Conduct tree-planting campaigns and restore forests throughout the basin.	2.883	Moderate extent
3.567	Great extent	10	Promote and facilitate the development and signing of local community conservation agreements.	2.067	Low extent
3.483	Moderate extent	11	Develop proposals for incentives for environmental services in significant areas of the target landscape.	1.650	Low extent
3.617	Great extent	12	Promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in land and water ecosystems in Nueva Vizcaya.	2.050	Low extent
3.617	Great extent	13	Promote environmental education programs on organic production and soil conservation.	2.050	Low extent
3.683	Great extent	14	Community education on the benefits of maintaining and conserving forests.	2.150	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	15	Training on seed preparation and community education on medicinal plant species and natural	1.683	Low extent

Importance				Practice	
Mean	QD		A. ENVIRONMENTAL	Mean	QD
			plant herbicides.		
3.533	Great extent	16	Community education on the long-term impacts of chemical fertilizers and pesticides on soil fertility, harvest quality, groundwater, and health.	1.683	Low extent
3.433	Moderate extent	17	Creation of nurseries of plants.	1.917	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	18	Community garden development in areas under a community forestry scheme.	1.950	Low extent
3.533	Great extent	19	Establishment of participatory decision-making and planning processes/mechanisms and knowledge sharing.	1.950	Low extent
3.500	Great extent	20	Establishment of local working groups, networks or associations of community organizations.	2.117	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	21	Documentation of environment friendly and traditional agricultural practices.	1.950	Low extent
3.633	Great extent	22	Raising environmental awareness and increasing the engagement of people in civic affairs.	2.283	Low extent
3.600	Great extent	23	Establish environmental protection council.	1.883	Low extent
3.373	Moderate extent	24	Promotion of fuel-efficient heating and cooking stoves.	1.483	Low extent
3.467	Moderate extent	25	Implement energy efficiency projects, e.g., promoting improved wood and charcoal stoves, contributing to reduced wood consumption, as well as planting hedgerows that can be used for fuelwood production.	1.483	Low extent
3.683	Great extent	26	Encourage residents to separate their garbage.	2.617	Moderate extent
3.717	Great extent	27	Set up programs to recycle recyclables.	2.633	Moderate extent
3.717	Great extent	28	Promote management and recycling of solid waste.	2.633	Moderate extent
3.633	Great extent	29	Provide strategic actions to help disaster-prone communities in reducing the risk of natural hazards and how they will manage disasters/calamities that may occur.	2.067	Low extent
3.616	Great extent		Overall	2.135	Low extent

Meanwhile, the respondents assessed extent of practice differently from extent of importance. While importance was rated either moderate or great, practice was rated from low to moderate. Eight of the 29 activities were rated practiced to a moderate extent, while almost three-fourths (72.41%) were rated practiced to a low extent. The top activities considered having great importance were practiced either to a moderate extent or low extent. Among those in the top list considered of great importance but practiced to a low extent are the following: raising environmental awareness and increasing the engagement of people in civic affairs; promoting the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in land and water ecosystems in Nueva Vizcaya; promoting environmental education programs on organic production and soil conservation; and community education on the benefits of maintaining and conserving forests. While SMU faculty and students conduct tree planting in some strategic places in the province, information campaign on the reasons behind the activity was not given emphasis. Moreover, the activities are conducted at most three times in every school year. Follow-up on whether or not the trees have grown was seldom carried out. Worse, people in the community take them away for fuel or for sale when the trees have already grown to a considerable height. Significant community stakeholders are not actively engaged in environmental educational programs, more so in helping protect their own environment.

Environmental sustainability involves ecosystem integrity, carrying capacity and biodiversity. It requires that natural capital be maintained as a source of economic inputs and as a sink for wastes. Resources must be harvested no faster than they can be regenerated. Wastes must be emitted no faster than they can be assimilated by the environment (Kahn, 1995).

Slaper & Hall (2011) posits that environmental variables should represent measurements of natural resources and reflect potential influences to its viability. It could incorporate air and water quality, energy consumption, natural resources, solid and toxic waste, and land use/land cover. Ideally, having long-range trends available for each of the environmental variables would help

organizations identify the impacts a project or policy would have on the area. Wanamaker (2018) agreed that proper management of natural resources is directly related to environmental sustainability.

Increasingly evident, resource constraints and deterioration across a number of environmental indicators including greenhouse gas emissions, air pollution, water stress, biodiversity loss and land degradation) are imposing both direct and indirect costs on human lives, health and welfare (Klarin, 2018).

C. ECONOMIC

In the economic area, only one activity out of 18 was rated important to a moderate extent. All the rest were considered important to a great extent; however, on top of the list are the following: a) support in the promotion of indigenous peoples' arts, crafts, and materials (clothing, woodcrafts, basket, clothing, etc.) (mean = 3.714); b) train clientele to be knowledgeable and competent on additional livelihood enterprises that could become added value in obtaining additional economic opportunities for target sectors like women, mothers, and or fathers (3.690); c) create cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge (mean = 3.667); d) train clientele to be knowledgeable and skilled in managing a business (mean = 3.661); e) product development and marketing of local products (mean = 3.661); and f) provide capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management (mean = 3.649). Generally, the respondents considered the activities important to a great extent.

While economic activities are considered greatly important, the overall mean of 1.890 suggests that the activities along this area are not practiced or practiced only to a low extent. This is not surprising because promoting indigenous peoples' arts, crafts, and materials, for instance, is only manifested during special occasions like *Ethnicity Week*, and *University Week wherein local traders are invited to occupy a place in the exhibit area where they can sell their local products*. Opportunities to promote local arts and culture are also seen during school programs, which are not considered extension activities.

Trainings on livelihood were also conducted by the School of Accountancy and Business under the *Entrep sa Barangay* Project. Monitoring and evaluation were also conducted to determine if the participants apply what they learned from the trainings. The preliminary evaluation of *Entrep sa Barangay* conducted by Villanueva, Adalem, Eslava, Garlitos and Garra in 2014 might further explain the ratings. The study noted that the beneficiaries acknowledged the support provided by Saint Mary's University particularly in terms of the livelihood project known as "*Entrep sa Barangay*". They also appreciate the full support and commitment of the faculty members and the students in providing them livelihood strategies through their projects and services. However, the beneficiaries suggested that a competition criteria/scheme in the implementation of the *Entrep sa barangay* project should be developed to encourage the beneficiaries to participate. They also suggested that materials and starting capital should be provided to motivate them to attend the livelihood trainings. The same suggestions were given in the study of Valtoribio, Jubay, Villanueva, and Taroma (2019) when the beneficiaries were asked about recommendations to improve the conduct of the trainings.

In the case of creating cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge, the SEAIT through its flagship program – *Tulongan sa Teknolohiya* is focused on sharing the expertise of its faculty including students in Civil, Electrical, Electronics and Communications, Computer Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology in promoting knowledge and skills on various technologies that will enhance and empower target groups and communities to apply basic carpentry, plumbing, basic electricity and electrical wiring installation, computer applications, basic arts and design, including those that pertain to climate change and disaster mitigation. (Valtoribio, Jubay, Villanueva, and Taroma (2019) revealed that the clients of *Tulongan sa Teknolohiya* were very much satisfied with the delivery of the activities and that their expectations were greatly met. They found the experiences with the activities very interesting and relevant to their needs. However, the clients revealed in the interviews that while they found the lectures very useful, time was inadequate for them to absorb everything. They request that follow-up sessions be conducted for them to cope and not to forget what they learned.

As to providing capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management, there has been no activity on this yet although the School of Health and Natural Sciences, particularly its Center for Natural Sciences, may be tapped to facilitate the work.

Table 3. Assessed Importance and Extent of Practice of Economic Activities

Importance		E. ECONOMIC		Practice	
3.42	Moderate extent	1	Develop and promote the use of traditional medicine from local plants and indigenous health practices.	1.817	Low extent
3.500	Great extent	2	Support for indigenous built and architecture to areas of spatial planning, housing, infrastructure development, and rural development in contemporary situations.	1.700	Low extent

Importance			E. ECONOMIC	Practice	
3.517	Great extent	3	Develop and promote indigenous methods and systems of dealing with food supply such as preservation, processing and production, as well as value addition through other approaches and the use of modern (bio-) technology.	1.850	Low extent
3.714	Great extent	4	Support in the promotion of indigenous peoples' arts, crafts, and materials (clothing, woodcrafts, basket, clothing, etc.).	2.267	Low extent
3.690	Great extent	5	Train clientele to be knowledgeable and competent on additional livelihood enterprises that could become added value in obtaining additional economic opportunities for target sectors like women, mothers, and or fathers.	2.300	Low extent
3.603	Great extent	6	Train small-scale or beginning entrepreneurs such as in meat or food processing, novelty items making and soap making.	2.050	Low extent
3.644	Great extent	7	Train clientele to be knowledgeable in the preparation of business plans.	1.983	Low extent
3.661	Great extent	8	Train clientele to be knowledgeable and skilled in managing a business.	2.017	Low extent
3.564	Great extent	9	Launch program to reduce automobile use.	1.317	Low extent
3.632	Great extent	10	Provide support for the development of the local tourism potential.	2.017	Low extent
3.621	Great extent	11	Train the community focused on the management of local natural resources.	2.050	Low extent
3.621	Great extent	12	Develop local capacities for local tourism potential.	1.883	Low extent
3.596	Great extent	13	Improve the access to credit and markets through development of appropriate business plans.	1.750	Low extent
3.638	Great extent	14	Strengthen the market chain for local products.	1.733	Low extent
3.661	Great extent	15	Product development and marketing of local products.	1.883	Low extent
3.667	Great extent	16	Create cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge.	1.950	Low extent
3.649	Great extent	17	Provide capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management.	1.933	Low extent
3.582	Great extent	18	Develop and promote traditional medicine from local plants.	1.517	Low extent
3.610	Great extent		Overall mean	1.890	Low extent

The respondents assessed extent of practice differently from extent of importance. While importance was rated either moderate or great, practice was rated as low. All the 18 activities were rated practiced to a low extent. The top activities considered having great importance were practiced to low extent. Among those in the top list considered of great importance but practiced to a low extent are the following: support in the promotion of indigenous peoples' arts, crafts, and materials (clothing, woodcrafts, basket, clothing etc.), train clientele to be knowledgeable and competent on additional livelihood enterprises that could become added value in obtaining additional economic opportunities for target sectors like women, mothers, and/or fathers, create cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge, provide capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management, and product development and marketing of local products. The Entrep sa Barangay Project of the School of Accountancy and Business conducted entrepreneurial and marketing seminars, product development activities, and bookkeeping training to the target beneficiaries. Information dissemination could be one of the problems since not all faculty members are aware that there were activities conducted related to livelihood. Inclusion of activities like support in the promotion of indigenous peoples' arts, crafts, and materials (clothing, woodcrafts, basket, clothing etc., create cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge, provide capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management, and product development and marketing of local products can be done to assist other target beneficiaries.

Slaper & Hall (2011) postulates that economic variables deal with the bottom line and the flow of money. It could look at income or expenditures, taxes, business climate factors, employment,

and business diversity factors. Specific examples include: personal income, cost of underemployment, establishment churn, establishment sizes, job growth, employment distribution by sector, percentage of firms in each sector, revenue by sector contributing to gross state product.

Communities that are well-planned with a variety of housing options, commercial developments and efficient and convenient transportation choices attract investments in new and expanded businesses. These investments can increase local economic activity and employment, saving time and money for employees and employers alike. Well-designed communities and efficient transportation are especially important for retaining and supporting the competitiveness of small to medium-sized businesses, which are the source of most employment growth. Communities that create opportunities for residents through sustainability practices to engage in physical activity and make healthy food choices generally have healthier residents. The economic benefits include lower healthcare costs for business, employees and public agencies, more productive employees, and students better prepared to learn.

Section 2. Proposed Action Plan

The Proposed Action Plan was based on the indicators of sustainability along environmental aspect, economic aspect, and social aspect as perceived by respondents with great importance but practiced to a low extent by the university which will be used to set directions for school flagship extension program.

Strategic Activity	Key Performance Indicator	Tactical Activities	Culmination Date	Remarks
A. ENVIRONMENTAL ASPECT				
Objectives:				
a. Promote the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in land and water ecosystems in Nueva Vizcaya.				
b. Promote environmental education programs on organic production and soil conservation.				
c. Promote community education on the benefits of maintaining and conserving forests.				
d. Raise environmental awareness and increasing the engagement of people in civic affairs.				
1. Launch SMU Biodiversity Project	At the end of Year 3, the SMU Biodiversity Project has already become operational.	1. Include conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in the Research Agenda of the Natural Sciences Department		
		2. Forge linkage with adapted community		
		3. Conduct Biological Diversity Researches		
		2.1 Genetic Diversity		
		2.2 Species Diversity		
		2.3 Ecosystem Diversity		
		4. Dissemination of results of researches conducted		
		4.1 Dialogue among the adapted community, government officials, etc.		
		4.2 Conduct Convention(s) on Biological Diversity		
2. Intensify Environmental Education Projects	At the end of Year 3, the adapted community embraces Organic Farming	1. Integrate environment awareness activities in the curriculum		
		2. Conduct environmental activities/events, e.g. (Earth Day celebration, Recycling of waste materials contests, etc.)		
		3. Create social media website/platforms		
		4. Conduct survey/research on		

		“Vegetable Farming Methods” of adapted community		
		5. Conduct seminar-trainings in adapted community:		
		4.1 Organic Production		
		4.2 Soil Conservation		
		6. Assist adapted community to embrace organic farming		
B. ECONOMICAL ASPECT				
Objectives:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Support in the promotion of indigenous peoples’ arts, crafts, and materials (clothing, woodcrafts, basket, clothing, etc.) b. Train clientele to be knowledgeable and competent on additional livelihood enterprises that could become added value in obtaining additional economic opportunities for target sectors like women, mothers, and or fathers. c. Create cooperation networks and support schemes to improve access and use of information and knowledge. d. Train product development and marketing of local products. e. Provide capacity building and technical assistance to train leaders for sustainable environmental management. 				
3. Intensify IP Projects		1. Increase involvement of schools in the Ethnicity Week Celebration.		
		1.1 Search for Best School in terms of IP products promotional and sales activities		
		1.2 Search for Most Creative IP Products		
		2. Establishment of IP Business Center		
		2.1 Conduct product development trainings/activities among IP partners		
		2.2 Conduct promotional activities		
		2.3. Conduct sales activities		
		2.4. Forge linkages with IP communities		
C. SOCIAL ASPECT				
Objectives:				
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Enhance IP capacities to lead in IP awareness, advocacy, education and training and other issues that concern them. b. Forge external linkages and intra-unit partnerships for the preservation, promotion and empowerment of the Indigenous Peoples. c. Work on Development Projects in collaboration with the Center’s internal units and external partners. d. Ensure that underserved and marginalized sectors are afforded continuing education on justice, peace and human rights. e. Subsidize food, health care, and education. 				
4. Intensify IP Advocacy Projects	At the end of Year 3, there will be additional 3 IP adopted communities.	1. Strict implementation of CMO No. 2, S. 2019 (Integration of IP Studies/Education into the Relevant Higher Education Curricula)		
		2. Collaborate with NCIP and other agencies regarding possible IP projects		
		3. Reorganize BIBAK Organization		
		4. Disseminate results of researches conducted		

		by students during the pandemic among IP groups		
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The study was undertaken to assess the sustainability performance of SMU Extension Services Programs in terms of extent of importance and practice along the following domains: social, environmental, and economic. An Action Plan was crafted to address challenges of the extension programs and set directions for future school flagship extension program.

The study adopted the mixed methods research design. The quantitative technique was used to generate the respondents' assessment of sustainability performance of the extension programs in terms of extent of importance and practice along social, environmental, and economic factors of sustainability. On the other hand, the qualitative techniques specifically document scanning and interviews were used to determine sustainability challenges to validate the responses derived from the survey conducted. The respondents and subjects of the study included stakeholders like Mission and Identity Coordinators, the LMCDAC director and staff, and community organizers of the different flagship programs of each school from SY 2015-2016 TO SY 2018-2019.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, there are social, economic, and environmental activities that are considered of moderate to great importance, and also either of moderate or great practice making such extension activities generally sustainable. The fact that many social, environmental, and economic activities are considered both as of moderate to great importance and moderate to great extent of practice signifies the positive values and attitudes that SMU stakeholders, particularly the implementers, hold towards the extension programs. Seeing that there are of great important extension activities but of little extent of practice signifies the SMU stakeholders' willingness to do more noble activities in the communities.

The study strongly recommends the following: (a) sustain the activities that are considered both as of moderate to great importance and of moderate and great practice; (b) review the activities that are of great importance but little extent of practice for consideration for future extension planning, if necessary and within the capability of the University; and (c) that the Action Plan formulated in this study be considered to set directions for school flagship extension program and training of faculty extensionists.

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